

THIN WALLED COMPOSITE SHELLS UNDER AXIAL IMPULSIVE LOADING

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1 General Introduction

The present study deals with "dynamic buckling", where a composite cylindrical shell, which is subjected to an axial impact load, loses its stability once its lateral transient behavior becomes unbounded in response to the applied impulsive load. Under this type of loading, a structure may survive suddenly applied loads, the amplitudes of which may exceed by many times its static buckling capacity before reaching its critical conditions, provided the loading duration is short enough. Hence, the load intensity is loading duration dependent, where the prescribed loading amplitude determines its maximum safe time of application. In the case under consideration, triggering of "dynamic buckling" is only possible in presence of relatively small lateral initial geometric imperfections, or lateral coupled deformations stemming from the cylinder skin constitutive relations. Instability in these cases results from continuous amplification of either the imperfections or the coupled deformations once they exceed permissible critical arbitrarily prescribed values of stress/strains or deformations.

Therefore, definition of "dynamic buckling" is arbitrary and consequently there is no unique criterion as yet for determination of "dynamic buckling", nor guidelines for design of dynamic buckling resistant structures exist. A criterion that lends itself to a rational definition of "dynamic buckling" has been proposed by Budiansky & Hutchinson [1, 2] and is depicted in Figs. 1&2. Following their criteria, dynamic instability will occur when a very small increment in the applied load given by

$$q(\vec{x}, t) = \lambda q_0(\vec{x}, t) \quad (t \geq 0)$$

(where $q(\vec{x}, t)$ represents an assembly of loading histories generated by λ in this equation, $q_0(\vec{x}, t)$ is a particular function of \vec{x} , and λ is a parameter) results

in a relatively large increase in the response strain, deflection etc. of the structure. This event defines the critical value of λ , or the maximum load for which a bounded response exists. One should note that because unlike in the static case the loading and response are time dependent, this analogy with static buckling is incomplete. Budiansky and Hutchinson's proposal for definition of the maximum load, for which a bounded response exists, was found to be a possible starting point in the search for a criterion that lent itself simple and to convenient experimental interpretation of dynamic stability. The advantage of employing the Budiansky-Hutchinson criterion is that it determines simplified means for definition of the critical dynamic loading without resorting to a direct solution of the time-dependent nonlinear partial differential dynamic equations that are derived in studying dynamic stability. It has, therefore, been adopted in the numerous test programs conducted at the Technion, Aerospace Structures Laboratories [3-6] and provided meaningful applicable results.

Fig.1. A simple imperfection sensitivity model
The Budiansky-Hutchinson modified version

It defines simplified means for determination of the critical dynamic loading, and in essence is analogous to ones employed in the definition of static buckling load of an imperfect structure. Thus, it provides means for comparison between static and dynamic buckling loads corresponding to a given structure;

however the analogy is incomplete since in the dynamic case the loading and the structural response are time dependent. In light of the above discussion wide range parametric numerical studies have been undertaken in the present study to assess the influence of shell wall configuration and its initial geometrical imperfections on the dynamic buckling capacity and behavior of thin walled composite shells, as well as on the loading duration of the shell, which in turn also affects the critical load capacity. In performing these evaluations the Budiansky & Hutchinson criterion has been adopted for determination of the shell critical dynamic load.

Fig.2. Budiansky-Hutchinson plot for determining the dynamic buckling parameter

As indicated above, structures that are exposed to the introduction of short duration impulsive loading can withstand "dynamic buckling" loads that significantly exceed their static buckling capacity, the shorter the loading duration the higher their magnitude. However, when approaching quasi-static conditions, the structure load carrying capacity equals its static buckling resistance. The question immediately arises as to whether there exist time durations within the above range of loading durations, for which the structure "dynamic buckling" capacity becomes lower than its static buckling resistance. The Technion Budiansky-Hutchinson criterion based on tests [3-6], demonstrated that indeed such a situation exists in the cases of columns and plates. For time durations that were equal, or close to the first time period of natural lateral vibration in bending of these structural elements dynamic buckling load amplitudes, smaller than the corresponding static

ones, were both found in calculations and observed in experiments (See Fig. 3).

Fig.3. Dynamic load amplification factor (DLF) vs. impact duration (a schematic view)

Of course, these observations have very important implications, and are very annoying from a design point of view. It is very important to find out whether they also apply to cylindrical shells. On the one hand shells are very initial geometrical imperfections sensitive. On the other hand, as shown above, existence of initial geometrical imperfections is a must to excite "dynamic buckling" of a structure. Furthermore, as indicated above, existence of initial geometrical imperfections increases the loading duration and consequently decreases the "dynamic buckling" capacity of a structure. Combining these arguments on the effects of initial geometrical imperfections it appears that they may play a major role in the "dynamic buckling" behavior of thin shells and *a priori* may lead to significant degradation of their "dynamic buckling" load carrying capacity, as well as may affect their response in the neighborhood of loading durations that are equal to the first time period of natural lateral vibration of the shell.

Therefore, the main goals, that the present research has undertaken, are to propose and provide such criteria and information that will contribute to the enhancement of our knowledge on pulse buckling, as well as provide designers with tools for safe design of shell structures to withstand their exposure to axial impulse (impact) loading. The present research focuses on "dynamic buckling" behavior of composite circular cylindrical thin-walled shell structures.

Another objective is to demonstrate the implementation of "dynamic buckling" criteria in calculations

Furthermore, as indicated above initial geometrical imperfections are a must to excite and experience "dynamic buckling". Also they lead to significant degradation in the static buckling capacity of a shell, as well as tending to increase the loading duration and thus decrease the shell dynamic buckling resistance. Therefore, the effects of shell signature, i.e. geometrical initial imperfections, loading imperfections and boundary conditions are also considered and assessed within the framework of the present study.

This study will focus its investigations in the troublesome range of loading durations, where "dynamic buckling" resistance is smaller than the static one. Since imperfection sensitivity of shell structure is associated with tedious nonlinear analysis, an attempt will be made to develop a semi-empirical approach to account for their presence.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1 Imperfection Assessment

Following the above introduction it is obvious that the presence of initial imperfections plays a major, if not the most important, role, both in dynamic and static buckling. There is no "dynamic buckling" unless a structure contains them. On the other hand, the impulsive (impact) loading duration depends on their typical magnitude, increases as they increase, and the longer the duration the lower the dynamic buckling resistance of the structure; static buckling is very sensitive to their presence, that may significantly reduce the static buckling load carrying capacity of a shell. This implies that real experimental studies have to start with initial imperfection measurements of the shell with given boundaries and loading conditions, to assess their influence on both the static and dynamic buckling capacities of the shell, in addition to the effects stemming from non-symmetry of the shell skin lay-ups and eccentric loading of the cylinder. Imperfection measurement is a very time consuming process. Reliable trusty data requires measurements of thousands of points of a shell surface. This situation is particularly unacceptable or rather impossible in the design stage of the shell. Therefore for practical purposes as an alternative it is proposed to resort to the assumption quite frequently applied in the static case, that presentation of the initial

geometrical imperfections by the first mode of buckling of the perfect nominal shell with appropriate amplitude would yield quite reliable results (knock down factors). Here, this type of imperfection will be referred to as an "artificial imperfection". The applicability and adequacy of this approach to assess the "dynamic buckling" capacity of composite shells have been initiated in [7]. These studies have indicated the proposed approach to be viable.

The above alternative approach has been further implemented and assessed in the present study. ABAQUS code [8] was employed to calculate the static buckling capacities of graphite/epoxy shell of two skin configurations, $[0^\circ, -45^\circ, +45^\circ]$, and $[-45^\circ, 0^\circ, +45^\circ]$, and of increasing amplitudes of initial geometrical imperfections with shapes corresponding to the first buckling mode of the perfect shell. The results are depicted in Fig. (4). One should notice that both shells were nominally clamped at their edges, they are 230 mm long (between clamped edges), 250 mm in diameter and made of graphite-epoxy with the following properties: $E_{11}=137.0$ GPa, $E_{22}=9.81$ GPa, $G_{12}=5.886$ GPa, and $\nu_{12}=0.34$, and 0.125 mm layer thickness.

Fig.4. Buckling load vs. initial imperfection amplitude

2.2 Dynamic Buckling Results

The procedure applied earlier for static buckling was applied again for the "dynamic buckling" phase. Numerical results were obtained with ABAQUS EXPLICIT code [25]. It should be noted that these results have been obtained by virtual test like

simulation procedures, in which the test procedures were followed to reduce the numerical results. The responses of the shell, with prescribed loading end plates, which were used in the tests, that has been exposed to impacts by a prescribed impactor employed in the tests and dropped from increasing heights on the upper loading plate, were calculated. Then, the compression and bending strains at the actual gage locations were calculated and a Budiansky-Hutchinson type curve (Fig. 2) was drawn to determine the dynamic critical compression strain according to the Budiansky-Hutchinson criterion. Like in the tests this procedure has been repeated for varying masses of the loading end plate. The results thus obtained have been plotted in a dynamic amplification, $\epsilon_{comp/cr} / \epsilon_{comp.st/cr}$ (where $\epsilon_{comp/cr}$ is the dynamic critical compression strain and $\epsilon_{comp.st/cr}$ is the static critical compression strain) vs. nondimensional impact duration $2T/T_b$ (where T is the impact duration and T_b is the lowest bending duration of the shell) domain. It should be noted that the equivalent artificial imperfections discussed above have been used in performing the calculations. A typical result is shown in Fig. 5 for the shell having a lay-up of $[0^\circ, -45^\circ, +45^\circ]$.

Fig.5. DLF vs. impact duration – Finite element predictions and experimental results.

Figure 5 shows in fact the **DLF** (**D**ynamic **L**oad **A**mplification **F**actor) as a function of twice the nondimensional duration of the impact. It shows three curves each having a different type of initial geometric imperfection, no imperfection (0h), a medium size imperfection (0.6h), similar to what was encountered in the test series ([7]) and a large imperfection (1.2h) for reference, where h is the shell thickness and equals 0.375 mm. The perfect

shell shows the same behavior as already found for columns and plates ([7-16]), namely in the vicinity of $2T/T_b = 1$, a **DLF** less than one is to be expected. This means that the dynamic buckling load is lower than the static ones. For lower values of $2T/T_b$, the **DLF** is well above 1, while for higher ratio of $2T/T_b$, the **DLF** slowly approaches unit value, meaning the dynamic behavior is a quasi-static one.

For shells with initial geometric imperfections, the behavior differs. In the range of duration $2T/T_b = 1$, a kind of irregular behavior has been observed, the dynamic buckling load decreases as we approach $2T/T_b = 1$, reaches a minimum value around $2T/T_b = 1$, then increases, reaches a local maximum, and continuously decreases towards the magnitude of the static buckling. This has been observed both for a shell with a mild geometric imperfection (0.6h) and larger one (1.2h), with the irregular behavior being moved to the right of the graph with increasing in the imperfection amplitude. One should note that the local minimum of both curves had the same value (DLF=1.2), but at different values of $2T/T_b$. Also, as expected, the greater the initial geometric imperfection, the greater the shell natural duration (lower natural frequency). It seems that the initial geometric imperfections have a lower influence on the dynamic buckling load as compared with the static one. This leads to a DLF greater than 1 for the whole range of the duration of the impact as compared to the shell first natural bending duration. This important conclusion has to be further verified, for other shell configurations.

The present test results, are engulfing the curve with a mild imperfection (0.6h) (see Fig.5), although only four test points are depicted.

To further understand the dynamic behavior of shells under impulsive loads, the calculated "dynamic buckling" patterns of the $[0^\circ, -45^\circ, +45^\circ]$ shell corresponding to two impact durations and quasi static loading are depicted in Figs. 5 a-c. It is apparent from these figures that the longer the loading duration the more developed the buckling deformation of the shell surface becomes. In the case of (a) where $T = 746 \mu$ Sec deformation buckling is

Fig. 6a. Dynamic buckling pattern of $[0 \mp 45]$ cylinder (loading end plate $M=3.2$ kg, Impact duration 746μ Sec)

Fig. 6b. Dynamic buckling pattern of $[0 \mp 45]$ cylinder (loading end plate $M=32$ kg, Impact duration 2170μ Sec)

Fig. 6c. Buckling of the composite cylinder $[0 \mp 45]$ in the quasi-static case

pronounced near the impacted end of the cylinder. With increase in T (Fig. 6b), the developed deformation surface has moved towards the lower un-impacted edge of the shell and under quasi static loading (Fig. 6c), the surface deformation becomes symmetrically fully developed, i.e. there is no

preference for either the impacted or non impacted edges of the shell.

The relative behavior of the impactor, loading end plate and shell at impact is of importance. It provides the necessary information about the responses during impact of the impactor and end plate at their interface, and of the end plate and upper shell edge at their interface, as well as serving as a means to determine impact duration. The force and displacement responses of the impactor, the loading plate and the edge of the shell at their interfaces, during the period of impact, area shown in Figs. 7 a and 7 b, respectively. It appears from these figures that whereas the impactor rebounds almost immediately after impact (Fig. 7a), contact time between the loading plate and the shell is significantly long (Fig. 7b). As has been found in the calculations, the mass of the impactor affects the magnitude of the applied impulse, while the mass of the loading end plate is merely responsible for the impact duration and consequently the magnitude of dynamic buckling load. It should be noted that the impactor rebounds only when its mass is smaller than that of the loading end plate. Otherwise, the impactor will rebound and strike the end plate more than once.

Fig. 7a. Behavior at interfaces (impactor and end plate and end loading plate and shell edge)-contact forces vs. time.

3. Conclusions

The Budiansky-Hutchinson criterion for definition of "dynamic buckling", because of its similarity to the static buckling definition provide a relatively

Fig. 7b. Behavior at interfaces (impactor and end plate and end loading plate and shell edge)-displacements vs. time.

simple, easy to apply tool, both for test and computational analyses, for rational definition of the dynamic buckling resistance of a cylinder. Particularly, this holds when comparing non-arbitrary static buckling with "dynamic buckling" to determine the dynamic load amplification factor, DLF, because of the common criterion employed for the definition of both buckling types.

The need to introduce imperfection to initiate the "dynamic buckling" causes significant difficulties, particularly in the numerical analysis. This requires tedious imperfection measurements of the shell to be tested, as well as very time consuming and costly numerical analysis, immaterial of the code employed to perform the analysis. It has been proposed to resort to the assumption, that in static buckling the influence of initial geometrical imperfections may be equivalently assessed by replacing the actual real imperfections by ones that correspond in their shape to the first static buckling mode of the perfect shell, for varying magnitudes of the amplitudes of these equivalent virtual imperfections. Using this assumption has significantly simplified the testing and numerical analysis. No more actual initial imperfections measurements were required. The magnitudes of the amplitudes of the equivalent imperfection surface of a given shell have been determined by comparing the experienced test results with a priori generated curves of the static buckling loads versus varying magnitudes of amplitudes of the first buckling mode of a corresponding perfect shell under consideration.

Good agreement of test results with predictions based on these virtual imperfection surfaces has been experienced. A numerical attempt has been made to verify the assumed hypothesis of the effect of impact loading duration on the dynamic buckling load amplification factor, **DLF**, presented in Fig. 3. Special emphasis has been given to loading durations in the neighborhood of the period of time that corresponds to the first natural bending vibration frequency. Unlike earlier studies with columns and plates, no dynamic buckling capacity, neither experimental nor predicted, smaller than the static one has been observed for any of the cylinders studied within the framework of the present research project, the results of which are reported herein.

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